

Tannic acid- and *N*-acetylcysteine-chitosan-modified magnetic nanoparticles reduce hepatic oxidative stress in prediabetic rats

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ABSTRACT

Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) modified with tannic acid (TA) have shown remarkable success as an antioxidant and antimicrobial therapeutic agent. Herein, we report a synthetic procedure for the preparation of silica-coated MNPs modified with *N*-acetylcysteine-modified chitosan and TA. This was achieved by free-radical grafting of NAC onto chitosan (CS), a layer-by-layer technique for modifying negatively charged MNP@SiO₂ nanoparticles with positively charged CS-NAC, and crosslinking CS with TA. The antioxidant and metabolic effects of MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC and MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA nanoparticles were tested in a model of prediabetic rats with hepatic steatosis, the hereditary hypertriglyceridemic rats (HHTg). The particles exhibited significant antioxidant properties in the liver, increasing the activity of the antioxidant enzymes superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione reductase (GR) and glutathione peroxidase (GPx), decreasing the concentration of the lipoperoxidation product malondialdehyde (MDA), and improving the antioxidant status determined as the ratio of reduced to oxidized glutathione; in particular, TA increased some antioxidant parameters. MNPs carrying antioxidants such as NAC and TA could thus represent a promising therapeutic agent for the treatment of various diseases accompanied by increased oxidative stress.

1. Introduction

Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) are one of the most commonly used inorganic materials in biomedical applications. The possibility of their remote control via an external magnetic field is mainly used in drug delivery systems and magnetic hyperthermia [1]. In the first case, MNPs serve as carriers to transport drugs or biologically active molecules to the target site. In the second case, they produce heat to sensitize tumor cells to chemotherapy or kill them directly. Other applications of MNPs include contrast agents, biosensors, and scaffold modifiers for tissue engineering. Among MNPs, iron oxide-based nanoparticles are commonly exploited due to their high biocompatibility, good magnetic properties and the various methods available for their controlled synthesis. However, degradation of MNPs may be accompanied by the production of reactive oxygen species capable of damaging cellular components or disrupting signaling pathways. For this reason, the particles are often coated with silica, serving as a mechanical barrier between the particle core and the environment. The silica coating also

facilitates further modification of the particle surface. While small molecules can be directly sorbed onto silica, silica functional groups can bind, e.g., polymers grafted with biologically active compounds. Synthetic and natural polymers are widely used to surface-modify nanoparticles to ensure their good colloidal stability in biological media, impede their clearance, and simplify drug delivery [2]. Polysaccharides are biocompatible and biodegradable polymers, broadly applicable for, e.g., drug delivery systems, tissue engineering, and wound dressings [2, 3]. In terms of chemical composition, polysaccharides consist of monosaccharide units linked by *O*-glycosidic bonds. However, due to the different types of possible monomer units, these polymers are varied. For example, chitosan (CS), the product of chitin deacetylation, contains randomly distributed β-(1→4)-linked *D*-glucosamine and *N*-acetyl-*D*-glucosamine units. CS itself has been the subject of numerous modifications to improve its water-solubility, antibacterial and antioxidant properties [4–6]. The free-radical grafting method is one of the simplest approaches to attach small biological molecules to CS; it requires mild reaction conditions and produces nontoxic byproducts. The method has

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so far been used to incorporate antioxidants, such as gallic acid, quercetin, caffeic and ferulic acid into CS [7–10]. Moreover, *N*-acetylcysteine (NAC)-grafted chitosan derivatives have already been reported as an effective protective agent against alcohol-induced liver and brain damage, as well as they have improved precorneal retention and ocular penetration compared to unmodified chitosan [11,12]. In turn, tannic acid (TA), a natural polyphenol, exhibits antioxidant effects and may alleviate oxidative stress, which plays an important role in the pathogenesis of metabolic chronic diseases including non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) [13].

The aim of this study was to develop novel MNPs with antioxidant properties capable of reducing oxidative stress in the liver cells of an experimental animal after their intravenous administration. In a rat model of metabolic syndrome associated with hypertriglyceridemia, we tested the hypothesis that binding of TA to MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC particles may show beneficial effect on hepatic lipid accumulation and oxidative stress in the liver.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), chitosan (CS, highly viscous) from crab shells, IGEPAL® CO-520, iron(II) chloride tetrahydrate, iron(III) chloride hexahydrate, Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent, *L*-ascorbic acid, *N*-acetylcysteine (NAC), tannic acid (TA), and tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). 25% Ammonia solution, 30% hydrogen peroxide, dichloromethane, ethanol, acetic acid, hexane, and oleic acid were obtained from Lach-Ner (Neratovice, Czech Republic). Ultra-high purity water used for synthesis and modification of MNPs was produced by a Milli IQ 7000 system (Merck Millipore; Burlington, MA, USA).

2.2. Modification of chitosan with NAC

A slightly modified free-radical grafting method was used to incorporate NAC into CS (Fig. 1) [7]. Briefly, CS (500 mg) was dissolved in 2% acetic acid (50 ml) and the solution was stirred at 23 °C overnight. Separately, *L*-ascorbic acid (54 mg) was dissolved in water (0.9 ml), supplemented with 30% hydrogen peroxide (0.1 ml) and added to the polymer solution. After 7 min, the polymer solution was mixed with the NAC solution (9.7 mmol in 40 ml of water) and stirred at 23 °C for 24 h. The resulting CS-NAC polymer was dialyzed against water for 48 h and

lyophilized. All steps were performed in the dark. Control CS was prepared by the same procedure but without NAC.

2.3. Synthesis of MNPs and silica-coated MNPs

Silica-coated MNPs were prepared as previously reported [14]. Briefly, an aqueous iron(II) and iron(III) chloride (2:1 mol/mol) solution was treated with ammonium hydroxide to form a black precipitate of particles later collected by a magnet and washed with water. To partially oxidize the magnetite nanoparticles, they were redispersed in water (205 ml), supplemented with 37% hydrochloric acid (150 µl) and 30% hydrogen peroxide (3 ml) and stirred at 70 °C for 1 h. The particles were then transferred to dichloromethane using oleic acid as stabilizer, washed with dichloromethane (3 × 10 ml) and hexane (2 × 10 ml) and redispersed in it (10 ml). The silica coating was prepared by the reverse microemulsion method. The oleic acid-stabilized nanoparticles (100 mg) were diluted with hexane to 10 ml and mixed with ammonia (0.540 ml) and IGEPAL® CO-520 (3 ml) by sonication with a Bandelin ultrasonic homogenizer (Berlin, Germany; amplitude 10%) for 30 min. Finally, the particles were mixed with TEOS (75 µl) and stirred at 23 °C for 24 h. The resulting MNP@SiO₂ nanoparticles were washed with ethanol (10 ml), ethanol/water (1:1 v/v; 10 ml) and water (2 × 10 ml).

2.4. Modification of MNP@SiO₂ nanoparticles with CS-NAC and TA

A layer-by-layer technique was used to modify the surface of negatively charged MNP@SiO₂ nanoparticles with the positively charged CS-NAC. The solution of CS-NAC (10 mg) in water (2 ml) was added to the MNP@SiO₂ nanoparticle dispersion (20 mg; 10 mg/ml), the mixture was vortexed at 23 °C for 30 min and the resulting MNP@SiO₂-NAC nanoparticles were washed with water (2 × 2 ml) and redispersed there (2 ml). To modify the particles with TA, a 1 mM aqueous solution of TA (2 ml) was mixed with MNP@SiO₂-NAC (20 mg; 10 mg/ml) dispersion and the mixture was shaken for 1 h. The particles were collected with a magnet, washed with water (2 × 2 ml) and redispersed in it. All steps were performed in the dark and using argon-purged water.

2.5. Characterization methods

Nanoparticle morphology and silica coating thickness were investigated from micrographs taken with a FEI Tecnai G2 Spirit transmission electron microscope (TEM; Brno, Czech Republic). Hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) and ζ -potential of the nanoparticles were measured using

Fig. 1. Scheme of particle modification with tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), *N*-acetylcysteine-chitosan (CS-NAC), and tannic acid (TA).

a Zetasizer Ultra (Malvern Panalytical; Malvern, UK) at 25 °C. The ATR-FTIR spectra were collected using a Bruker IFS 55 FTIR spectrometer (Billerica, MA, USA) equipped with a mercury cadmium telluride detector and a Specac MKII Golden Gate Single Reflection ATR System (Specac; Orpington, UK) with a diamond crystal (angle of incidence 45°). The spectra were collected with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and 64 accumulations. TGA was measured in air using a Pyris 1 thermogravimetric analyzer (PerkinElmer; Waltham, MA, USA) over a temperature range 30–800 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. ¹H NMR spectra were measured on a Bruker Avance III 600 spectrometer (Billerica, MA, USA). The Folin-Ciocalteu's assay was used to determine antioxidant properties of solutions of CS or CS-NAC polymer (~10 mg) in water (2 ml) as previously reported [8]. Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (100 µl) was mixed with a solution of CS-NAC (20 µl) in water (1.58 ml) and 16.6% aqueous sodium carbonate (300 µl). The absorbance was measured after 90 min at 765 nm with five replicates. The gallic acid equivalent (GAE) was calculated from the gallic acid calibration curve. The GAE, corresponding to mg of gallic acid per g of polymer, was expressed as the mean ± standard deviation (SD) of three independent experiments. The ability of the polymers and particles to scavenge free radicals was evaluated using DPPH. A series of polymer solutions or particle dispersions of decreasing concentration (dilution factor = 1.36) were prepared. A 0.1 mM solution of DPPH in ethanol (600 µl) was added to a solution of the polymer or particle dispersion (200 µl) in ethanol (1.2 ml), the mixture was left in the dark for 30 min, particles were removed by filtration through a PTFE hydrophilic syringe filter with a pore size of 0.45 µm, and the absorbance was read at 517 nm; each measurement was tripled. The mean half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) was calculated from three and two independent measurements of polymers and particles, respectively.

2.6. Administration of nanoparticles in an experimental rat model

The hereditary hypertriglyceridemic (HHTg) rat strain, was used to investigate the antioxidant and metabolic effects of MNPs *in vivo*. This rat strain serves as an animal model of metabolic syndrome, which exhibits dyslipidemia, impaired glucose tolerance, tissue resistance to insulin action, fatty liver and chronic low-grade inflammation in the absence of obesity [15,16]. Animals were fed a maintenance diet for rats and mice (Altromin; Lage, Germany) and given free access to food and water. Nine-months old male rats were randomly divided into four groups: untreated rats (saline; n = 4), rats treated with MNPs (control group; n = 8), MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC (n = 8), or MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA nanoparticles (n = 7). Once a week (every Monday), particle dispersions (40 mg/ml) were administered intravenously into the *vena caudalis* at a dose 250 µl for four weeks. Untreated rats were injected intravenously with 250 µl of saline. At the end of experiment, three days after last nanoparticle application, rats were sacrificed under anesthesia and blood serum and tissue samples were collected and stored for subsequent analysis. All experiments were performed in agreement with the Animal Protection Law of the Czech Republic (No. 311/1997) and the Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council and were approved by the Ethics Committee of the Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic (protocol No. 37/2022).

2.7. Basal metabolic analysis of an animal model

Serum levels of triglycerides (TAG), glucose and total- and HDL-cholesterol were measured using commercially available kits (Erba Lachema; Brno, Czech Republic, and Roche Diagnostic Mannheim, Germany). Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) enzyme activity and non-esterified fatty acid (NEFA) were determined spectrophotometrically using Roche Diagnostics kit. To determine concentrations of TAG and cholesterol in the liver, tissue samples were powdered under liquid nitrogen and extracted in a

chloroform/methanol mixture. The organic phase was evaporated under nitrogen, the resulting pellet was dissolved in isopropyl alcohol and the triglyceride and cholesterol content was determined by enzymatic assay (Erba Lachema).

2.8. Oxidative stress parameters

The antioxidant enzyme activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and glutathione reductase (GR) were measured using commercially available kits (Sigma-Aldrich and Cayman Chemicals; Ann Arbor, MI, USA). Malondialdehyde (MDA), a lipid peroxidation parameter, was determined by HPLC with fluorescence detection, while 4-hydroxynonenal (4-HNE) by rat ELISA (MyBiosource; San Diego, CA, USA). The levels of reduced (GSH) and oxidized (GSSG) forms of glutathione were determined by HPLC with fluorescence detection using an HPLC diagnostic kit (Chromsystems Instruments & Chemicals; Gräfelting, Germany). Relative hepatic mRNA expression of nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor (Nrf2) was determined by quantitative real-time PCR analysis using the TaqMan RNA-to-CT 1-step kit, TaqMan gene expression assay and ViiA™ 7 real time PCR system (ThermoFisher Scientific; Waltham, MA, USA). Relative expression was determined after normalization against *Actb* as an internal reference and then calculated using the 2^{-ΔΔC_t} method [17].

2.9. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA with Fisher's post hoc test with Statistica 14 software and data were expressed as mean ± SEM. Group comparisons were made with the MNF control group; *p* < 0.05 indicated a statistically significant result.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. CS-NAC polymer

Free-radical grafting is a useful approach to incorporate various antioxidants, including gallic acid, catechin, phloroglucinol into chitosan [7,8]. This procedure was also used in the grafting of NAC onto chitosan in this study (Fig. 2). The advantage of NAC lies in its antioxidant property and biocompatibility, which allows its widespread application in clinical practice in the treatment of paracetamol-damaged liver. Chitosan, which is also biocompatible, was used as the NAC carrier. Moreover, it is positively charged, therefore it readily adsorbs onto negatively charged MNP@SiO₂ particles.

The resulting CS-NAC polymer was characterized by ATR-FTIR and ¹H NMR spectroscopy (Fig. 3). In the ATR-FTIR spectrum of CS (Fig. 3a), a broad peak at 3290 cm⁻¹ corresponded to O-H and N-H stretching vibration, a peak at 2864 cm⁻¹ was assigned to C-H stretching, a peak at 1644 cm⁻¹ was attributed to amide I and peaks at 1033 and 1066 cm⁻¹ corresponded to C-O skeletal stretching vibrations [18]. In contrast, new peaks at 1375 and 1583 cm⁻¹ corresponding to carboxyl groups and stretching vibration in -N-H group of NAC, respectively, appeared in the spectrum of CS-NAC. In the ¹H NMR spectra of CS-NAC and NAC, multiplets were recorded at 2.45 ppm (attributed to -SH), 2.80 ppm (assigned to -C-H in -CH₂), 3.35 ppm and 4.6 ppm (originating from -CH (NH); Fig. 3b). In the spectrum, a shift of the multiplet corresponding to proton „c“ was observed. In contrast, no shifts were observed for protons „a“ and „b“. This suggests that a carboxyl or amide group may be involved in the bond formation between chitosan and NAC, with the carboxyl group being more prone to bond formation. Both FTIR and NMR spectra thus confirmed the binding of NAC to CS. The antioxidant properties of CS and CS-NAC were evaluated by the Folin-Ciocalteu's method and expressed as GAE. In contrast to CS, the absorbance of CS-NAC at 765 nm was ~12-fold higher. The GAEs for CS and CS-NAC were 4.0 ± 0.2 and 59.3 ± 1.2 mg/g of polymer, respectively, demonstrating the strong antioxidant properties of CS-NAC due to the presence

Fig. 2. Modification of chitosan with *N*-acetylcysteine (NAC) by free-radical grafting.

of NAC. CS-NAC was also superior to CS regarding its ability to scavenge free radicals (Fig. 3c). The IC_{50} for CS was 0.69 ± 0.08 mg/ml, whereas it was more than three times lower for CS-NAC (0.20 ± 0.02 mg/ml). Interestingly, the free-radical scavenging ability of CS-NAC was similar to that of hydroquinone-modified CS and an order of magnitude lower than that of gallic acid-modified CS [8].

3.2. MNPs and MNP@SiO₂ nanoparticles and their modifications with CS-NAC and TA

MNPs were prepared in two steps according to our previously described procedure [8]. In the first step, magnetite nanoparticles were prepared by coprecipitation of iron chlorides, which were partially oxidized in the second step to form a maghemite layer around the magnetite core. The preparation of MNPs was followed by coating with a silica and modification with CS and possibly TA, which is known for its ability to crosslink chitosan. The silica was introduced to isolate the NAC from the iron oxide. In addition, silica-coated particles are known for their colloidal stability in aqueous media, hydrophilicity and nontoxicity.

According to TEM micrograph, the MNPs were semispherical in

shape and exhibited a non-uniform size distribution ($D = 0.33$) with a number-average diameter D_n of 11 nm (Fig. 4a). Hydrodynamic diameter (D_h) and polydispersity (PD) of MNPs was 138 nm and 0.15, respectively, indicating their slight aggregation in water; however, the positive ζ -potential of 32 mV indicated good colloidal stability of the particles (Table 1). On the TGA curve, the initial weight loss (2.2 wt%) observed up to 350 °C was attributed to the removal of crystalline water (Fig. 4c). The FTIR spectrum of the MNPs showed an intense peak at ~ 600 cm^{-1} corresponding to Fe-O vibrations, two peaks at 1436 and 1623 cm^{-1} originating from C-O stretching and O-H bending vibrations, respectively, and one additional broader peak at 3380 cm^{-1} assigned to O-H stretching vibrations (Fig. 4d) [19]. The ability of MNPs to scavenge free radicals ($IC_{50} = 0.56 \pm 0.001$ mg/ml) was almost three times higher than that of CS-NAC (Fig. 4e).

In the TEM micrograph of MNP@SiO₂ nanoparticles, silica was visible as a thin layer (3 nm thick) with lower density surrounding the magnetic core (Fig. 4b). The significant increase in D_h (by 107 nm) and PD (by 0.07) compared to MNPs indicated particle clumping, but this was not associated with a loss of dispersion stability; only a small change in the absolute value of the ζ -potential was observed (Table 1). The negative charge of MNP@SiO₂ particles originated from the presence of

Fig. 3. (a) ATR-FTIR spectra of control CS and CS-NAC; (b) ¹H NMR spectra of NAC, control CS and CS-NAC and (c) dependence of DPPH inhibition on polymer concentration.

deprotonated silanol (Si-OH) groups on their surface [20]. In TGA, the weight loss of water (1.4 wt%) was observed for the particles heated up to 460 °C, followed by gradual weight increase of 0.5 wt% up to 800 °C due to magnetite oxidation (Fig. 4c). In the ATR-FTIR spectrum, the silica coating was documented by an intense peaks at 969 and 1066 cm⁻¹, both attributed to the Si-O-Si stretching vibrations (Fig. 4d) [21]. Compared to MNPs, silica-modified nanoparticles showed a significantly lower ability to eliminate DPPH radicals (Fig. 4e); the $IC_{50} = 3.32$ mg/ml was almost six times higher, suggesting that the iron atoms on the surface of the MNPs were involved in the scavenging of DPPH radicals, while the silica coating effectively prevented the interaction between DPPH and the core. Consequently, it can be said that silica coating provides higher colloidal stability of the particles and may

limits the toxicity associated with the uncontrolled degradation of MNPs. The adsorption of CS-NAC on the silica coating had a negligible effect on the hydrodynamic parameters; only the ζ -potential changed from negative to positive due to the amino groups of chitosan. Modification of MNP@SiO₂ particles by CS-NAC led to the weight loss observed in the TGA curves (Fig. 4b). At 440 °C, the total weight loss of MNPs@SiO₂-CS-NAC was 2.9 wt%, of which 1.5 wt% was attributed to the thermal decomposition of CS-NAC. This demonstrated the existence of interactions between silica and CS-NAC. The small amount of CS-NAC bound to the particle surface caused that the ATR-FTIR spectra of MNP@SiO₂ particles and MNPs@SiO₂-CS-NAC particles did not differ. Binding of CS-NAS to MNP@SiO₂ slightly improved (by 14.5%) the free radical scavenging ability (Fig. 4e); the IC_{50} value determined for MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC particles was 2.84 ± 0.11 mg/ml.

The crosslinking of the CS-NAC layer of MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC particles with TA was accompanied by an increase in the dispersion stability of the particles in water (D_h decreased by 34 nm) and a change in the charge to negative (ζ -potential = -27 mV) due to carboxyl groups of TA (Table 1). It is worth mentioning that MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA particles exhibited the lowest polydispersity ($PD = 0.11$) among all the prepared nanoparticles because of improved stabilization by TA. It should also be noted that TA is more water soluble than chitosan due to the presence of many hydroxyl groups, which also contributes to the good colloidal stability of MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA particles in water. The decomposition of the organic phase in the MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC particles was observed in the TGA curves up to 520 °C, with a total weight loss attributable to TA of 3.2 wt% (Fig. 4b). In the ATR-FTIR spectra, the presence of TA was documented by the appearance of new peaks between 1320 and 1705 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 4d, e). While the peaks in the vicinity of 1300 cm⁻¹ were attributed to the vibrations of C-C, C-OC and C-OH carbons in the aromatic rings, the peaks at 1700 cm⁻¹ corresponded to C=O vibrations [22]. The presence of TA on the outer layer of MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA particles significantly improved their ability to eliminate free radicals; $IC_{50} = 0.0308 \pm 0.0004$ mg/ml was almost 20-fold and 100-fold lower compared to MNPs and MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC particles, respectively.

3.3. *In vivo* effect of selected nanoparticles on metabolic and oxidative stress parameters in HHTg strain of rat

NAFLD, the most prevalent chronic liver disease affecting up to a third of the adult population, is closely associated with metabolic diseases such as type 2 diabetes mellitus, metabolic syndrome and dyslipidemia [23]. Therefore, the *in vivo* effect of MNPs, MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC and MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA nanoparticles on hepatic oxidative stress and lipid accumulation was investigated in prediabetic rat model with fatty liver. Compared to MNPs, the exposure of MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC and MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA particles did not alter whole body weight, relative weight of kidney and heart and slightly changed relative weight of liver of HHTg rats (Table 2). Serum activity of hepatic enzyme ALT slightly increased after application of CS-NAC- and CS-NAC-TA-modified nanoparticles, while activity of AST did not change, indicating that the particles did not have harmful effects and suggesting their biocompatibility (Table 2). Since NAC is commonly used as a drug [24], it can be assumed that NAC-modified particles are biocompatible and well tolerated by the body.

After administration of both MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC and MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA nanoparticles, there were no differences in non-fasting glycemia, as well serum lipid parameters, i.e., cholesterol, HDL-cholesterol and NEFA; however, the serum TAG concentration decreased (Table 2). Beneficial effect of TA on serum lipid parameters was shown in another model of metabolic syndrome, the spontaneously hypertensive rat [25]. The hypolipidemic effects of TA could be related to its ability to bind to molecules associated with blood lipid levels [26]. Treatment of HHTg rats with MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC and MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA particles did not affect hepatic lipid

Fig. 4. TEM micrographs of (a) neat and (b) silica-coated MNPs; (c) TGA curves, (d) ATR-FTIR spectra and (d) DPPH inhibition by the nanoparticles.

Table 1

Characterization of particles by dynamic light scattering.

Nanoparticles	D_h (nm)	PD	ξ -potential (mV)
MNPs	138	0.15	32
MNP@SiO ₂	245	0.22	-27
MNP@SiO ₂ -CS-NAC	248	0.22	22
MNP@SiO ₂ -CS-NAC-TA	214	0.11	-27

D_h – hydrodynamic diameter, PD – polydispersity.

accumulation and did not change hepatic TAG or cholesterol concentration (Table 3); nevertheless, NAC can improve liver function and protect against hepatotoxic agents [27,28].

Oxidative stress, which results from an imbalance between pro- and antioxidant levels, is involved in the pathogenesis of NAFLD and plays a key role in the progression of liver disease to liver fibrosis, cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma [29]. To investigate the *in vivo* effect of MNPs, MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC and MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA nanoparticles on oxidative stress in the liver and to determine the possible antioxidant properties of the particles, the antioxidant enzyme activities,

Table 2

Basal metabolic and serum parameters of HHTg rats untreated and treated with nanoparticles.

	Saline	MNPs	MNP@SiO ₂ -CS-NAC	MNP@SiO ₂ -CS-NAC-TA	<i>p</i> _{ANOVA}
Body weight (g)	476 ± 6	452 ± 17	442 ± 9	462 ± 9	n.s.
Heart weight (g/100 g)	0.194 ± 0.004	0.191 ± 0.003	0.199 ± 0.004	0.199 ± 0.003	n.s.
Kidney weight (g/100 g)	0.499 ± 0.017	0.490 ± 0.009	0.498 ± 0.007	0.499 ± 0.015	n.s.
Liver weight (g/100 g)	3.058 ± 0.056	3.037 ± 0.035	2.926 ± 0.035	3.185 ± 0.097	<0.05
TAG (mmol/l)	6.88 ± 1.02	4.97 ± 0.38 ^d	2.40 ± 0.14***	2.55 ± 0.13***	<0.001
Cholesterol (mmol/l)	2.37 ± 0.08	2.24 ± 0.07	2.25 ± 0.07	2.19 ± 0.04	n.s.
HDL-cholesterol (mmol/l)	0.67 ± 0.01	0.64 ± 0.02	0.68 ± 0.03	0.60 ± 0.03	n.s.
NEFA (mmol/l)	0.67 ± 0.06	0.61 ± 0.05	0.55 ± 0.05	0.55 ± 0.05	n.s.
Non-fasting glucose (mmol/l)	8.20 ± 0.38	8.28 ± 0.35	9.18 ± 0.39	9.10 ± 0.45	n.s.
ALT (μkat/l)	1.24 ± 0.07	1.25 ± 0.04	1.80 ± 0.11*	1.82 ± 0.26*	<0.05
AST (μkat/l)	3.10 ± 0.27	3.23 ± 0.34	3.23 ± 0.23	3.48 ± 0.32	n.s.

Data are expressed as mean ± SEM; # *p* < 0.01 denotes significant difference between saline vs. MNPs, * *p* < 0.05 and *** *p* < 0.001 denote significant difference between MNPs vs. MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC or MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA particles. TAG – triglycerides, NEFA – non-esterified fatty acids, ALT – alanine aminotransferase, AST – aspartate aminotransferase; n.s. – not significant. One-way ANOVA and LSD Fisher post-hoc test.

Table 3

Effect of nanoparticles on lipid and oxidative stress parameters in the liver of HHTg rats.

	Saline	MNPs	MNP@SiO ₂ -CS-NAC	MNP@SiO ₂ -CS-NAC-TA	<i>p</i> _{ANOVA}
Cholesterol (μmol/g)	5.97 ± 0.57	5.89 ± 0.45	6.30 ± 0.34	6.21 ± 0.43	n.s.
TAG (μmol/g)	14.81 ± 1.60	14.20 ± 0.74	14.30 ± 0.76	16.65 ± 1.38	n.s.
4-HNE (pg/mg protein)	0.255 ± 0.024	0.261 ± 0.026	0.292 ± 0.035	0.242 ± 0.027	n.s.
GSH (μmol/mg protein)	66.06 ± 2.06	62.79 ± 1.37	64.03 ± 1.76	67.43 ± 1.54	n.s.
GSSG (μmol/mg protein)	2.66 ± 0.21	2.16 ± 0.15 [#]	1.46 ± 0.08***	1.57 ± 0.15**	<0.001
GSH/GSSG	25.28 ± 1.94	30.03 ± 1.98	44.76 ± 2.74***	45.24 ± 4.19***	<0.001
CAT (mM H ₂ O ₂ /min/mg protein)	0.950 ± 0.003	0.966 ± 0.003	0.961 ± 0.003	0.944 ± 0.014	n.s.
Nrf2 (relative expression)	1.008 ± 0.074	1.018 ± 0.076	0.880 ± 0.042	0.930 ± 0.059	n.s.

Data are expressed as mean ± SEM; # *p* < 0.05 denotes significant difference between saline vs. MNPs, ** *p* < 0.01 and *** *p* < 0.001 denote significant difference between MNPs vs. MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC or MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA particles. TAG – triglycerides, 4-HNE – 4-hydroxynonenal, GSH – reduced form of glutathione, GSSG – oxidized form of glutathione, CAT – catalase; n.s. – not significant. One-way ANOVA and LSD Fisher post-hoc test.

glutathione concentrations and lipoperoxidation parameters in the liver were determined. The increased activity of the glutathione-dependent GPx and GR enzymes after the exposure to both MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC and MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA nanoparticles could contribute to the reduction of the concentration of the oxidized form of glutathione and the improvement of GSH/GSSG ratio in the liver (Fig. 5 and Table 3).

GSH/GSSG ratio is a marker of cellular health, indicating the balance between oxidative stress and antioxidant status. Thus, increased GSH/GSSG ratio can reduce intracellular oxidative stress [30]. NAC, a precursor of reduced GSH, can act as a reactive oxygen species scavenger and counteracts oxidative stress especially on hepatic tissue [31]. NAC was shown to increase GSH levels in hepatic cells, which increased their protection capability and stimulated the activity of antioxidant enzymes, such as GR [32]. In addition, the activity of another antioxidant enzyme, SOD, was significantly increased after administration of both MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC and MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA particles (Fig. 5). Moreover, SOD and GR activities increased more after MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA treatment than that of MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC, suggesting that MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA exhibited higher antioxidant activity than MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC. The hepatoprotective effects of TA can be attributed to its strong antioxidant properties. It was previously found that TA increased hepatic SOD and GPx levels in acetaminophen-induced hepatotoxicity in mice [13].

In our study, TA-containing MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC particles increased radical scavenging capacity (Fig. 4e). *In vivo*, the activation of SOD and GR in the liver was more efficient after MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA application than after MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC, which was consistent with the results of the DPPH assay. The lower ability of MNPs to reduce oxidative stress compared to MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC particles, despite the demonstrated lower IC₅₀ value in the DPPH assay, was probably due to radical formation via a Fenton-type reaction [33]. The relative hepatic mRNA expression of the transcription factor Nrf2, which regulates the expression of antioxidant enzymes, was not affected by nanoparticle administration (Table 3), suggesting that the nanoparticles activated antioxidant enzymes directly rather than through the increased expression of Nrf2. Moreover, the level of one of the most important lipoperoxidation products, MDA, was reduced in the liver after administration of MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC and MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA particles (Fig. 5). Excessive production of MDA is associated with various pathological conditions including cancer, diabetes and liver disease [34]. Also, the concentration of another lipid peroxidation product, 4-HNE, did not change after nanoparticle application (Table 3).

In summary, MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA nanoparticles did not affect lipid accumulation in the liver but exhibited significant antioxidant properties. Since oxidative stress significantly contributes to the progression of hepatic steatosis and there is no approved pharmacological treatment for NAFLD, our novel antioxidant nanoparticles could represent a promising new therapeutic agent for the treatment of hepatic disorders, tumors and diabetes.

4. Conclusions

Antioxidant-containing nanoparticles have recently gained increasing attention as protective agents against atherosclerosis, cancer and neurodegenerative diseases. In this work, CS-NAC-coated MNPs were prepared for the first time, in which TA was readily incorporated to boost the antioxidant activity of the agent. The advantage of the magnetic properties of the particles is based on the possibility of their controlled transport by magnetic field, visibility on MRI, nontoxicity, biocompatibility and last but not least the fact that they are FDA approved for anemia treatment [35]. Tannic acid- and *N*-acetylcysteine-chitosan-modified magnetic nanoparticles exhibited significant antioxidant effects in the liver mediated by increased antioxidant enzymes activity, reduced lipid peroxidation and improved antioxidant status. The addition of TA to CS-NAC-coated MNPs enhanced some parameters of the antioxidant effect, especially in the case of superoxide dismutase and glutathione reductase. MNPs coated with CS-NAC and CS-NAC-TA favorably affected oxidative stress in the prediabetic rat model, thereby protecting it from oxidative damage. These novel particles may thus be useful in the antioxidant therapy of various diseases accompanied by oxidative stress, such as cardiovascular and liver diseases, diabetes mellitus or cancer.

Fig. 5. Effect of nanoparticles on (a) activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD), (b) glutathione peroxidase (GPx), (c) glutathione reductase (GR) and (d) concentration of lipoperoxidation product malondialdehyde (MDA). ### $p < 0.001$ denotes significant difference between saline vs. MNPs, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ and *** $p < 0.001$ denote significant difference between MNPs vs. MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC or MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA particles, § $p < 0.05$ and §§§ $p < 0.001$ denote significant difference between MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC vs. MNP@SiO₂-CS-NAC-TA particles.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Marková Irena: Writing – original draft, Conceptualization.
Malínská Hana: Methodology. **Hüttl Martina:** Investigation.
Miklánková Denisa: Formal analysis. **Černá Kristýna:** Methodology.
Konefal Rafał: Methodology. **Horák Daniel:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Świątek Małgorzata:** Writing – original draft, Investigation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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